

HIGH-FIDELITY SIMULATIONS OF THE FLOW UNSTEADINESS IN THE ROTOR OF A TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR STAGE

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ABSTRACT

Flows in modern compressors are highly complex. They are subject to adverse pressure gradients, high levels of unsteadiness and often operate at transonic conditions. Such conditions often render design tools based on low order methods unreliable. This is due to the inherently unsteady nature of shock-boundary layer interaction as well as the interaction between deterministic and stochastic unsteadiness. These issues are further exacerbated by the current design trends towards more compact machines with higher work coefficients. It is therefore desirable to study the flow unsteadiness within a transonic compressor stage using high-fidelity scale resolving simulation. To enable fully wall resolved stage calculations at a realistic rotor Reynolds number of 1×10^6 , a quasi three-dimensional translational setup was carefully generated to feature similar midspan blade loadings to the three-dimensional rotational set up of the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt. The aim of the paper is to study the flow unsteadiness of the transonic compressor stage exposed to turbulent inflow using highly resolved large eddy simulation. The results focus on the characterization of the various sources of unsteadiness as well as their interactions. It is found that the rotor shock system unsteadiness is coupled both to the inflow, via free-stream particles passing through the shocks of the adjacent blades, and to the trailing edge unsteadiness, most likely through a feedback loop.

Keywords: Shock-Boundary Layer Interaction, Unsteady Aero-

dynamics, Large Eddy Simulations

NOMENCLATURE

c Speed of sound.
 u', v', w' Velocity fluctuations.
 x, y, z Cartesian coordinates.
BPF Blade passing frequency fL/U
 C Chord.
 C_{ax} Axial chord.
 F_{red} Reduced frequency.
 Ma_r Mach number based on inlet cond. of rotor.
 Ma_s Mach number based on inlet cond. of stator.
 Re_r Reynolds number based on inlet cond. and chord of rotor.
 Re_s Reynolds number based on inlet cond. and chord of stator.
 T Rotor time period.
 U_e Boundary layer edge velocity.
 Φ Flow coefficient.
 Ψ Work input coefficient.
 ρ Density.
 $\rho u, \rho v, \rho w$ Momentum components.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a pressing demand for highly efficient, robust and above all sustainable drive trains for the aviation transportation

sector as well as the generation of electrical energy, especially against the background of a steadily growing economy and the accompanying anthropic climate change. Although engine efficiency has increased significantly over the last decades, additional gains are essential to ensure that aviation's contribution to climate change will not further grow. Research and development departments in industry, government and academia have made important steps in the last decades in further developing and improving the design tools required for this purpose.

New commercial aero engines for 2050 will have lower specific thrust to improve propulsion efficiency and reduce noise. Nevertheless, these engines will not meet the ambitious fuel consumption and emissions targets of Flightpath 2050 [1] and the European Green Deal [2] without radical developments in engine cores to improve thermal efficiency. Disruptive technologies for this purpose include measures such as intercooling, recuperation, inter-turbine combustion, etc. In addition to robust and efficient operation, a key requirement for these, and also conventional future gas turbines, is a much more compact and thus lighter design. In addition to the reduction in mass flow, however, the reduction in the size of the core leads to ever smaller and faster rotating blades with higher loads in order to realize the necessary pressure ratios at high efficiency. The compressor within a turbomachine is an example of an essential component that plays a crucial role for future drive trains and propulsion systems.

Efficiency, reliability and noise of turbomachinery compressors are significantly influenced by the unsteady flow phenomena during operation. High Mach numbers and compression shocks lead to complex shock-boundary layer interactions (SBLI). These interactions can change the local flow behavior and hence lead to a generation of additional loss and noise sources. The four relevant regions which can have an effect on the unsteadiness of the shock boundary layer interaction according to Hergt et al. [3] are upstream in front of the SBLI, the boundary layer state downstream of the shock foot and at the trailing edge as well as the shock itself within the cascade's passage. Upstream of the SBLI region, both the degree of inflow turbulence as well as the associated state of the boundary layer, and in case of a laminar-turbulent boundary layer transition, the modes of transition, have an effect on the unsteadiness of the shock. For example, e.g. Dussauge et al. [4], show that the instability of a possible (laminar) separation bubble below the shock affects the shock wave oscillation. This is also confirmed in Bode et al. [5] by means of highly resolved LES with different inflow turbulence intensity affecting both the boundary layer transition and the shock wave oscillation. This is also supported by the experimental results in Hergt et al. [6]. They showed that an increased level of inflow turbulence changed the oscillation behaviour of the shock but they concluded that this was not only due to the higher turbulence level itself, but rather from the resulting turbulent shock-boundary layer interaction. According to Lee [7], a shock-induced boundary layer separa-

tion downstream at the trailing edge of a single airfoil and the resulting turbulence structure of the wake results in sound waves and their propagation from the trailing edge upstream toward the shock and hence excitation of the shock oscillation is supposed to occur through these transient sound waves, cf. [8]. In Priebe et al. [9] wall-resolved LES of a transonic tip region section at five unique operating conditions were conducted. The results support the physical mechanism of the unsteadiness and associated frequency scaling based on turbulent structures convecting downstream from the shock to the trailing edge followed by acoustic disturbances traveling from the trailing edge upstream to the shock. Contrary to that, Crouch et al. [10] found that the shock oscillation is induced by pressure fluctuations moving downstream around the trailing edge and propagating upstream on the pressure side towards the leading edge and influence the shock. The separation bubble region has previously been shown to significantly contribute to the noise generation. In [11] the effect of Mach number on the surface pressure spectrum of a subsonic controlled diffusion airfoil was investigated. A wavenumber–frequency decomposition was used to separate hydrodynamic and acoustic components showing that the source of the greater acoustic contribution at the trailing edge of the airfoil can be traced back to the separation bubble near the leading edge. Recently Hergt et al. [3] concluded from extensive experimental results and comparison to numerical and experimental results from literature that contrary to the mechanism described above, neither the boundary layer state and behavior upstream of the shock nor the turbulent boundary layer behavior downstream of the shock and at the trailing edge induces a strong shock-wave oscillation self-excitation. No acoustic waves could be detected coming from the area of the trailing edge in the direction of the shock. Hence, in [3] a new mechanism of self-excited shock oscillation was introduced where the shock oscillation causes an unsteadiness of the inflow angle in front of the shock foot which leads to a change in the shock position as well as structure and in this way could excite the shock-wave oscillation itself.

Thus, there are still many unanswered questions like the role of the shock-boundary layer interaction especially on the noise generation and ambiguous results as described above that point to the need for further research with high-resolution methods such as LES. Furthermore, most studies have not considered significant free-stream turbulence and adjacent blades, which considerably increase flow complexity and makes it hard to identify sources of unsteadiness and noise.

Therefore, the aim of the presented paper is to characterize the flow unsteadiness of a modern transonic compressor stage under free stream turbulence conditions using highly resolved large eddy simulation and describe the various sources of unsteadiness as well as their interactions.

2 METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Configuration

The initial configuration for the test case investigated here is the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt (TCD) single stage geometry open source test case available via The Global Power and Propulsion Society (GPPS) [12]. The TCD represents a high-pressure compressor front stage comprising a BLISK rotor (16 blades) designed by MTU Aero Engines and a 3D-optimized stator (29 vanes) designed and conjointly realized by DLR and the Institute of Gas Turbines and Aerospace Propulsion at TU Darmstadt [13]. To make high-resolution wall-resolved LES possi-

FIGURE 1. TRANSONIC COMPRESSOR DARMSTADT AT DESIGN POINT: TRANSLATION FROM 3D ROTATIONAL (LEFT) TO 2D TRANSLATIONAL (RIGHT) WHICH WAS USED FOR THE LES STUDY.

ble, the original TCD configuration was simplified in two steps: firstly, a scaled version was created with a rotor/stator ratio of 1:2 to allow computation of just one rotor and two stators with periodic pitchwise boundary conditions. Secondly, a streamtube around the mid-section region was chosen and translated from a 3D rotational into a Q3D translational framework, as shown in Fig. 1. More details on the derivation of the configuration and the numerical setup are found in [5] and [14], which focused on studying the impact of inflow conditions, and rotor-stator gap variations ($\pm 25\%$) on the flow behavior and losses, respectively. The flow conditions, i.e. the Reynolds number, Mach number, flow and work coefficients as well as non-dimensional blade passing frequency ($BPF = fL/U$) for the Q3D translational LES are given in Tab. 1.

TABLE 1. TEST-CASE DETAILS AND INFLOW CONDITIONS.

Re_r	Re_s	Ma_r	Ma_s	Φ	Ψ	BPF	Tu_∞
$1 \cdot 10^6$	$7 \cdot 10^5$	0.935	0.525	0.60	1.86	1.64	2%

FIGURE 2. INSTANTANEOUS COMPRESSOR STAGE VISUALIZATION USING SPANWISE VELOCITY ISOSURFACES AND DENSITY VARIATION ON THE SPANWISE PLANE (TOP).

2.2 Numerical Method

The LES were performed using the in-house compressible multi-block structured flow solver, HiPSTAR [15]. The research tool HiPSTAR (High-Performance Solver for Turbulence and Aeroacoustics Research) was developed to conduct cutting-edge DNS, i.e. the solution of the fully nonlinear, time-dependent and three-dimensional Navier–Stokes equations without any empirical closure assumptions, on today’s High Performance Computing (HPC) systems. Subsequently, subgrid-scale models were implemented that also provide LES capability, greatly reducing computational cost at higher Reynolds numbers. In the current study, fourth-order accurate spatial and temporal discretization was used, and the Wall-Adaptive Local Eddy viscosity (WALE) subgrid scale model [16] provided mathematical closure. A sliding interface method [17] was applied to enable full stage simulations. The fluid is modeled as a perfect gas with properties of cold air and the ratio of specific heats equals 1.4. Inflow turbulence was generated using a compressible-flow extension of the digital filter approach of Klein et al. [18].

The computational domain around the compressor blade was meshed using an O-grid that was overlaid on a Cartesian background mesh with an overset method [19]. The rotor blade domain and each stator blade domain were discretized with 768,000 and 320,000 grid points in the cross plane, respectively. The background mesh for the rotor and stators had 1.664×10^6 and 1.703×10^6 grid points in plane, respectively. A spanwise extent of 20% rotor chord was used and 320 points were used to discretize the spanwise direction for all domains, resulting in a total grid count of $\approx 1.528 \times 10^9$ points for the test cases. The resulting wall resolution in viscous coordinates was $\Delta x^+ \leq 25$, $\Delta y^+ \leq 3$ and $\Delta z^+ \leq 25$. Mesh independence of the results was confirmed by performing an additional LES on a finer mesh, see [5]. The stage case was run until the pressure ratio of 1.43 was reached and the transient part of the simulation had passed.

An instantaneous flow snapshot of the compressor stage simulation is shown in Fig. 2.

To aid the analysis, the statistics were collected over 16 rotor wake passing periods and consisted of time-averaged flow-fields along with 1,300 instantaneous spanwise snapshots taken at regular intervals (approximately 72 every rotor wake period). As a result, the unsteady pressure and velocity signals are available at every in-plane point in the domain to allow the spectral analysis of the flow.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the Mach numbers present within the rotor are much higher than those present within the stator, this study will primarily focus on the rotor bladerow and flow unsteadiness associated with it. Figure 2 highlights the strong shock on the rotor suction side indicated by the density field in the x-y plane as well as spanwise velocity isosurfaces that visualize the turbulent boundary layers and wakes. Before the identification of noise sources and the quantitative influence of the shock-boundary layer interaction is discussed, the general flow behavior on the rotor is described.

3.1 Mean flow behavior

Figure 3, showing time-averaged Mach number contours, gives an impression of the mean flow behavior. The black line signifies a free-stream streamline traveling through the full stage, from the inlet to the outlet of the computational domain. A particle following this streamline into the passage will first pass through a shock system of an adjacent blade. This has an impact on the flow unsteadiness as will be discussed in more detail later on. The rotor shock system is comprised of the following components: an oblique leading edge shock that forms when the flow accelerates around the leading edge and reaches a maximum speed of $Ma \approx 1.3$; a normal shock located at an effective blade passage throat that decelerates the flow rapidly. The normal shock foot coincides with the rotor suction side separation which is intermittently suppressed due to the free-stream disturbances injected into the boundary layer near the leading edge. The general time-averaged flow behavior on the suction side of the rotor is characterized by an initially laminar boundary layer, which undergoes transition to a turbulent boundary layer due to the shock-boundary layer interaction. In contrast to the case with a laminar inflow, cf. Bode et al. [5], the boundary layer transition takes place under the influence of free-stream turbulence via a bypass transition. This is evident from the formation of streaky structures due to the turbulence interaction at the leading edge and the creation of turbulent spots visible upstream of the shock and transition location in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 3. TIME-AVERAGED MACH NUMBER PLOT WITH AN EXAMPLE STREAMLINE PASSING THROUGH THE STAGE.

3.2 Pressure response

To quantitatively investigate the flow unsteadiness we compute pressure spectra at the planes identified by dashed lines in Fig. 4 (top) corresponding to locations: far upstream of the rotor bladerow (bottom left), between the rotor and the stator (bottom middle) and downstream of the stator bladerow (bottom right). In each plot the blade passing frequency (BPF) and its harmonics are marked with the red dashed lines. Each black line on the pressure power spectral density (PSD) plot corresponds to a one-dimensional PSD in time at a location along the pitch with the red line representing the spectrum obtained from averaging over all pitchwise locations. The location upstream of the rotor shows

FIGURE 4. PRESSURE POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY PLOTS ALONG THE PITCH AT THREE LOCATION CORRESPONDING TO UPSTREAM, MID-STAGE AND DOWNSTREAM.

a broadband peak centered around a non-dimensional frequency of ≈ 0.9 and another smaller one at ≈ 2.5 . There are also increased amplitude levels in the spectrum between the blade passing frequency and its harmonics, i.e. about the frequency of ≈ 5 . Another peak is present between the 3rd and 4th harmonic of the blade passing frequency. The remainder of the spectrum follows a $-5/3$ slope, signifying its link to the inflow turbulence (spectrum shown later). The spectra obtained between the rotor and the stator show a much more tonal behavior, with the peaks corresponding to the blade passing frequency and its harmonics. The lower frequency broadband peak is centered around roughly half the BPF and thus is a sub-harmonic related to the rotor-stator interaction. At this location, the remainder of the spectrum follows more closely a -1 slope which might be due to the turbulent free-stream flow facing an adverse pressure gradient in this region [20]. The spectra downstream of the stator look similar to the spectra in the rotor-stator gap, with strong blade passing frequency harmonics presence and the higher frequencies following a -1 slope. The spectra at this location also feature sub-harmonic peaks at half and one-quarter the BPF, which are even more prominent than in the gap.

3.3 Sources of flow unsteadiness

When flow unsteadiness and the corresponding acoustic signature of compressors is studied, the inflow is often kept clean, i.e. a laminar inflow condition is applied. However, this does not reflect the reality as transonic compressor stages are typically exposed to a turbulent inflow. As has been found in previous studies, e.g. [5], whether the inflow is laminar or turbulent can affect the SBLI behavior on the rotor suction side significantly, in that the transition behavior of the leading edge boundary layer is modified and the separation bubble location and size change. Figure 5 shows contours of the magnitude of the density gradients for the compressor stage under investigation here, with either a laminar or turbulent inflow. It can be seen that not only is the shock system on the rotor slightly different in the turbulent inflow case, but there are also additional interactions between the inflow turbulence with the blade boundary layers and wakes that can give rise to unsteadiness.

3.3.1 Inflow We first consider any unsteadiness related to the inflow conditions. The turbulent inflow prescribed here corresponds to isotropic turbulence with 1.6% turbulence intensity in a rotor frame of reference and a turbulent length scale of 6% rotor chord, which is representative of previously measured compressor turbulence levels [21]. Figure 6 shows the inflow velocity spectra along the pitch. The plot shows broad turbulence spectra with well-developed inertial regions that match Kolmogorov's $-5/3$ law. Compared to the bottom left subfigure of Fig. 4, the spectra are missing the broad low-frequency peaks that occur closer to the rotor. This suggests that these peaks are

FIGURE 5. INSTANTANEOUS COMPRESSOR STAGE VISUALIZATION USING DENSITY GRADIENT MAGNITUDE FOR THE LAMINAR (TOP) AND TURBULENT (BOTTOM) INFLOW.

not a feature of the inflow turbulence and arise as a result of stage interactions downstream which are then carried upstream. The inflow turbulence spectrum also shows no signature of the BPF.

3.3.2 Rotor shock system Another source of unsteadiness results from an unsteady motion of the shock system. To visualize the shock system unsteadiness, Fig. 7 shows $Ma = 1.0$ isolines obtained from 1,300 time instances, corresponding to approximately 10 rotor through-flows. The shock appears effectively fixed at the leading edge, but its instantaneous location spreads out the further away from the blade it is, which is due to its interaction with the free-stream turbulence. Interestingly, a large fraction of the second leg of the shock also appears to be fixed in space and shows little effective movement. This is presumably because it is a normal shock that corresponds to the effective passage throat. However, the second leg of the shock shows some movement at the foot where the interaction with the boundary layer separation causes it to move forward towards the leading edge by up to 4% of the blade chord. To better understand the unsteadiness of the shocks we will look at each shock in more detail in the following sections.

FIGURE 6. VELOCITY POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY PLOTS (BLACK) AND THEIR AVERAGE (RED) ALONG THE PITCH AT AN UPSTREAM LOCATION.

FIGURE 7. UNSTEADY $Ma=1$ CONTOUR PLOT SHOWING THE UNSTEADINESS OF THE SHOCK SYSTEM.

Leading-edge shock To understand the unsteadiness of the leading-edge shock we construct an instantaneous space-time diagram of Mach number parallel to the suction surface of the rotor blade and track the $Ma = 1.0$ isoline. We do this for two planes, one located close to the blade surface, another one further away. Figure 8 shows the space-time diagram at a plane close to the blade (left) and tracks the first shock front. To the right spectra of the unsteady shock movement are shown at a location close to the blade (solid line) and further away from it (dotted line). Unsurprisingly, the spectrum amplitude is much higher away from

FIGURE 8. SPACE-TIME DIAGRAM OF MACH NUMBER NEAR THE BLADE SURFACE AND SPECTRA OF THE LEADING EDGE SHOCK OSCILLATION RESULTING FROM TRACKING $Ma=1$ NEAR THE BLADE SURFACE (SOLID) AND AWAY FROM IT (DOTTED).

the blade as would be expected from Fig. 7. However, both spectra highlight certain frequencies of interest, which correspond to non-dimensional frequencies of ≈ 0.9 , 1.6 , as well as an elevated amplitude level between 1BPF and 2BPF. The spectrum obtained from data closer to the blade also features a peak at frequency ≈ 15 , while the spectrum obtained further away shows one at ≈ 20 .

Shock 2 For the second shock we again construct an instantaneous space-time diagram of Mach number parallel to the suction surface at two different wall-normal planes, away from the rotor, and track the $Ma = 1.0$ isoline. The location of the plane closer to the surface corresponds roughly to where the shock foot is located and where the shock-separation interaction is likely to occur. The plane located further away from the surface is located in the free-stream, where free-stream turbulence induced shock oscillations might occur. In Fig. 9 we see the opposite trend to the one observed for the leading edge shock, namely that the spectrum for the location further away from the rotor exhibits a lower amplitude (as would be expected from Fig. 7). However, as before we see both spectra pointing towards a similar set of frequencies, i.e. a low frequency broad peak at ≈ 0.9 and several peaks between 1BPF and 2BPF. In addition there are some peaks at frequencies marginally lower than 1BPF and between 2BPF and 3BPF.

3.3.3 Flow separation To characterize the flow separation unsteadiness we follow a similar procedure as for the shock unsteadiness. However, here we construct a space-time diagram of the surface shear stress and track the 0 velocity-gradient

FIGURE 9. SPACE-TIME DIAGRAM OF MACH NUMBER NEAR THE BLADE SURFACE AND SPECTRA OF THE SECOND SHOCK OSCILLATION RESULTING FROM TRACKING $MA=1$ NEAR THE BLADE SURFACE (SOLID) AND AWAY FROM IT (DOTTED).

FIGURE 11. PRESSURE POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY PLOT AT A LOCATION AHEAD OF THE TRAILING EDGE ON THE SUCTION SURFACE.

FIGURE 10. SPACE-TIME DIAGRAM OF SHEAR STRESS ON THE BLADE SURFACE AND A SPECTRUM OF THE SEPARATION OSCILLATION RESULTING FROM TRACKING $\tau_{wall} = 0$.

isoline, see Fig. 10. The separation movement along the blade surface corresponds to roughly 5% of the blade chord and results in a spectrum with elevated amplitudes from a frequency ≈ 2.5 up to ≈ 6 . Larger spectrum amplitudes can also be observed between 2BPF and 3BPF.

3.3.4 Trailing edge The trailing-edge often plays a major role in generating unsteadiness, both by creating vortical disturbances and as an acoustic source, especially at high Mach numbers [22]. Compressors often have very thin trailing edges which in combination with high Reynolds and Mach numbers implies that they do not feature significant vortex shedding. To

assess that assumption and to see the impact of the trailing edge on the pressure response here we compute a pressure spectrum near the trailing edge (at 0.99 surface distance), shown in Fig. 11. Several peaks can be identified that correspond to frequencies of ≈ 2 , 1BPF and 2BPF, as well as broad peaks at higher frequencies of ≈ 25 . These higher frequency peaks have been verified to get stronger the closer one gets to the trailing edge. They correspond to Strouhal numbers of $\approx 0.1 - 0.15$, based on the trailing edge thickness and the local boundary layer edge velocity.

3.3.5 Downstream stator Finally, the unsteadiness in the rotor-stator gap is quantified. The interaction between the rotor blade-row and downstream stator blade-row would be expected to be one of the main sources of unsteadiness. This is verified by computing the pressure PSD at a plane mid-stage. The impact of the rotor-stator interaction is clear from Fig. 12 as the BPF and its harmonics feature very clearly. In addition, lower frequency peaks at ≈ 0.9 and ≈ 1.6 (the BPF sub-harmonic) are present. However, their impact on the upstream part of the flow appears to be limited as these peaks were mostly missing from the results presented so far.

3.4 Coupling of unsteady dynamics

Thus far, we have quantified the unsteadiness present at select characteristic locations in the flow. In the following, we attempt to investigate how the unsteadiness might be coupled between various locations, with the aim at ultimately elucidating the origin of the unsteadiness.

Given the overall complex flow field, there are many dynamics at play as shown earlier. These dynamics are unlikely to act in isolation, however, and likely interact with one another and

FIGURE 12. PRESSURE POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY PLOT IN ROTOR-STATOR GAP.

couple together. This was alluded to in the previous section by pointing out certain frequency peak that occur at multiple locations. In this part of the paper the coupling of these dynamics will be described in more detail to reveal mechanisms driving the observed unsteadiness.

3.4.1 Inflow - shock system We start by looking at how the inflow couples with the shock system. Figure 13 shows the unsteady motion of the shock system and a time-averaged streamline impinging onto the leading edge of the rotor. Included are also properties along the streamline such as velocity, flow angle, Mach number and turbulence intensity. As a particle travels with the free-stream it is deflected twice, the first time by an unsteady shock system originating two rotor blades away, then by the shock system of an adjacent rotor before arriving at the blade leading edge. This is reflected by the particle's proper-

FIGURE 13. INTERACTION OF THE UNSTEADY INFLOW AND THE SHOCK SYSTEM RESULTING IN MATCHING INFLOW ANGLE AND SHOCK UNSTEADINESS SPECTRA.

FIGURE 14. DISTRIBUTION OF INFLOW ANGLE (LEFT) AND ITS SPECTRUM (RIGHT) AT TWO LOCATIONS: FAR UPSTREAM (BLACK) AND AHEAD OF THE LEADING EDGE (RED).

ties, e.g. a change in Mach number as it passes through each shock system. In the first instance, the particle does not pass directly through the shock system, as highlighted in Fig. 13, instead in instantaneous terms it passes through the shock only intermittently and so its mean velocity remains below $Ma = 1$, though it can instantaneously rise above. Changes at the second shock system are more drastic and show a particle reaching up to $Ma = 1.1$. As a result of this interaction, the inflow receives and imparts some unsteadiness onto the rotor and its shock system. How much unsteadiness is received/imparted is possibly related to the residence time within the shock and can be further visualized by plotting the effective angle of attack at each point along the streamline showing how it gets deflected in and out of the shock, Fig. 13. To further highlight the coupling between the inflow and the shock system we show a distribution of inflow angle at two locations: far upstream and ahead of the leading edge, Fig. 14. The inflow distribution figure shows that the incidence can vary instantaneously by up to $\pm 3^\circ$ for this case. The ‘perturbing’ impact of the shock on the inflow angle is further shown with a probability density distribution, which reveals that the standard deviation increases ahead of the shock. In addition spectra of the variations of the inflow angle at the two locations are provided, with the spectrum obtained close to the leading edge clearly featuring many of the frequencies previously found for the leading edge shock and shock 2 locations, c.f. Fig. 15. In addition, both spectra show broad high frequency peaks simi-

FIGURE 15. INFLOW ANGLE (RED) AND LEADING EDGE SHOCK (BLUE) OSCILLATION SPECTRA COMPARISON.

lar to the ones found in the trailing edge spectrum, which could potentially point to an additional trailing edge - inflow coupling.

3.4.2 Shock system - separation As mentioned previously, the suction side of the rotor is characterized by an initially laminar boundary layer, which undergoes transition to a turbulent boundary layer due to the shock-boundary layer interaction and features intermittent suppression of the separation due to the influence of free-stream turbulence. This is further shown in Fig. 16, which plots Mach number contours and tracks the

FIGURE 16. GROWTH OF INSTABILITIES WITHIN THE ROTOR BOUNDARY LAYER AND TRANSITION TO TURBULENCE AHEAD OF THE SEPARATION AND ITS INTERACTION WITH THE SHOCK.

FIGURE 17. SPACE-TIME DIAGRAM OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE FLUCTUATIONS ON THE SUCTION SIDE OF THE ROTOR (LEFT) AND CORRESPONDING 1D POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY ALONG THE SURFACE DISTANCE (RIGHT).

development of an instability which becomes unstable ahead of the shock front. This early transition thickens the boundary layer and is likely to pull the shock forward. In addition, the eddies embedded in the boundary layer result in local flow acceleration and more unsteady shock foot oscillation. To investigate the potential coupling between the shock system unsteadiness with the separation bubble unsteadiness, we show the space-time plot of pressure fluctuations on the suction surface and the 1D pressure spectra along the blade surface in Fig. 17. The spectra show that after the leading edge shock several low frequencies get excited which then tend to decay ahead of the second shock. Right ahead of the second shock a strong pressure signature of the separation oscillation can be seen between non-dimensional frequency of 2.5 and 6, before all the frequency amplitudes increase at the second shock location. Once a turbulent boundary layer develops the pressure spectra still show preference for certain frequencies which persist all the way to the trailing edge. Some of these

FIGURE 18. SECOND SHOCK (MAGENTA) AND SEPARATION (GREEN) OSCILLATION SPECTRA COMPARISON.

frequencies share a similar signature with the spectrum of the pressure oscillation. This is further highlighted in Fig. 18 which compares the spectra of the second shock oscillation and the separation oscillation where similarly elevated frequency amplitudes can be observed between frequencies of 2.5 and 6.

3.4.3 Trailing edge - shock system In order to investigate the potential coupling of the trailing edge unsteadiness with that of the shock system, we perform a two-dimensional frequency-wavenumber decomposition in the free-stream and close to and on the blade surface for velocity and pressure, respectively, shown in Fig. 19 and 20. Several characteristic wave speeds can be identified in these wavenumber-frequency plots, including downstream traveling hydrodynamic fluctuations in the free-stream (with speed U_e) and in the boundary layer (with speeds $0.5U_e$ and $0.75U_e$), downstream propagating acoustic waves (with speed $U_e + c$) and upstream propagating acoustic waves (with speeds $U_e - c$ and $0.6U_e - c$). Due to the tran-

FIGURE 19. WAVENUMBER-FREQUENCY SPECTRUM OF VELOCITY (TOP) AND PRESSURE (BOTTOM) IN THE FREE-STREAM.

FIGURE 20. WAVENUMBER-FREQUENCY SPECTRUM OF VELOCITY (TOP) AND PRESSURE (BOTTOM) CLOSE TO AND ON THE BLADE SURFACE.

sonic conditions over the rotor, the upstream traveling acoustic waves are more likely to travel within the boundary layer than in the free-stream, such that their velocity can be estimated by $U_e - c$, while the downstream propagating acoustic waves have speed $U_e + c$. Interestingly, the wavenumber-frequency spectra of velocity and pressure result in different estimates of the speeds of the downstream traveling hydrodynamic fluctuations and the upstream propagating acoustic waves. The pressure spectrum shows higher hydrodynamics fluctuation speeds and lower upstream propagating acoustic wave speeds. This suggests two different sources of unsteadiness propagating through the boundary layer, one related to vortical unsteadiness, another related to an acoustic source. Further still, a potential cone seen in the figures points to the presence of compressible pressure fluctuations and an acoustic resonance within the transonic compressor passage, presumably resulting from the pressure waves traveling upstream and downstream interacting with each other. Figure 21 shows a comparison between the trailing-edge pressure spectrum and the second shock oscillation spectrum (left) and the separation os-

FIGURE 21. SECOND SHOCK OSCILLATION (MAGENTA) AND TRAILING EDGE PRESSURE (BLACK) SPECTRA COMPARISON (LEFT) AS WELL AS SEPARATION OSCILLATION (GREEN) AND TRAILING EDGE PRESSURE (BLACK) SPECTRA COMPARISON (RIGHT).

cillation spectrum (right). On top of several matching lower frequency peaks, a broad higher frequency peak around frequency of 25 related to trailing-edge shedding is visible in the separation oscillation spectrum, suggesting the trailing-edge unsteadiness plays a role in modulating higher frequency separation oscillations.

4 CONCLUSION

Highly resolved large-eddy simulations of a modern transonic compressor stage midspan section at engine representative Mach and Reynolds numbers were performed. Instantaneous flow data was collected to carry out spectral analysis of the flow and investigate the flow unsteadiness in particular on the stage rotor. The focus of this study is to identify and characterize the unsteadiness with a particular focus on the inflow, shock-boundary layer interaction and the trailing edge, and how unsteadiness at different locations might couple with other locations. The results show a coupling between the incoming flow and the shock system which interact as the free-stream flow passes through the shock systems of adjacent blades. This results in matching spectra between the incidence and the leading edge shock oscillation. Correlation between various spectra suggests that the mechanism for this coupling is related to the residence time of a free-stream particle passing through the shocks of the adjacent blades and through that interaction unsteadiness is exchanged between the inflow and the shock system. In addition the results indicate that some of the frequencies observed in the spectra in the vicinity of the shocks and separation are not related to those contained in the inflow or to the blade passing frequency, but are similar to those seen at the trailing edge. This suggests a coupling of the separation bubble and shock system unsteadiness with the trail-

ing edge unsteadiness. The available data hint at this coupling being driven by a feedback loop, in which separation bubble unsteadiness convects downstream through the suction side boundary layer and gets scattered at the trailing edge, with the resulting acoustic wave then propagating upstream through the boundary layer and exciting the separation bubble. A rigorous validation of this conjecture is the subject of ongoing work.

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